

Metrics of antibiotic prescription or consumption to support antibiotic stewardship in the outpatient healthcare setting: A protocol for a scoping review

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Abstract

Introduction: Qualitative and quantitative metrics are needed to assess antibiotic consumption and prescription in the context of improving antibiotic stewardship programs in outpatient healthcare settings. This project aims to answer the research question "What metrics evaluate antibiotic prescription and consumption in the outpatient setting?" and to assemble an updated compilation of literature mentioning such metrics.

Methods: A scoping literature review will be conducted, following the PRISMA-guidelines and Joanna Briggs Institute methodology. Inclusion criteria will be: Studies that are performed in the outpatient setting, addressing systemic antibacterials, and using quantitative or qualitative metrics or proxy indicators as an outcome. The search strategy will focus on the databases Medline and Embase (via Ovid). Consecutively, two independent reviewers will perform the two screening phases (title-abstract screening and full-text screening), before the metrics will be extracted.

Results: Eligible studies will be presented in a PRISMA flowchart, and the findings will be described narratively. The collected metrics will be clustered into suitable categories.

Discussion: This scoping review will synthesize metrics that assess antibiotic consumption and prescriptions in the outpatient setting, considering different levels of data aggregation such as healthcare provider level, regional and national trends. It will be the first stepping stone to develop a core outcome set of such metrics for the ambulatory care setting in Switzerland to support and improve antibiotic stewardship.

Keywords

Anti-bacterial agents, antibiotic consumption, antibiotics, antimicrobials, antibiotic use, antibiotic prescription, outpatients, metrics, antibiotic resistance, antimicrobial stewardship, antibiotic stewardship

Introduction

Objective

To describe the metrics that evaluate antibiotic prescription and consumption in the outpatient healthcare setting.

Rationale

Bacterial antimicrobial resistance (AMR) occurs when bacteria no longer respond to drugs usually used to treat bacterial infections. According to the estimation of Murray et al. there were around 4.95 million deaths associated with bacterial AMR in 2019. [1] Additionally, the World Health Organization (WHO) states that "*The emergence and spread of drug-resistant pathogens threatens our ability to treat common infections and perform life-saving procedures including cancer chemotherapy, caesarean section, hip replacements, organ transplantation and other surgeries. In addition, drug-resistant infections impact the health of animals and plants, reduce productivity in farms, and threaten food security. AMR has significant costs for both health systems and national economies overall. For example, it creates need for more expensive and intensive care, affects productivity of patients or their caregivers through prolonged hospital stays, and harms agricultural productivity. AMR is a problem for all countries at all income levels. Its spread does not recognize country borders.*" [22] Bacterial AMR leads to considerable burden globally and it has emerged to be a leading threat to public health. [1]

A major key factor in increasing antibiotic resistance rates is antibiotic use, for instance misuse or overuse of antibacterial drugs. [2]

Antimicrobial stewardship is referred to as optimization of antimicrobial use (including antibacterial use). Antimicrobial stewardship programs or interventions contain a vast set of actions, mostly including the core component monitoring of antimicrobial use and resistance. Other action encompasses supporting audit of and feedback for prescribers. [3] In order for such actions to take place, metrics are needed to evaluate trends in antibiotic consumption and assess appropriateness of antibacterial drug prescriptions. Such metrics can be divided into three categories: quantity metrics, quality metrics and proxy indicators. [4-6]

Indicators can be distinguished into [5]:

- structure indicators, which describe prerequisites and general framework of healthcare systems (e.g. presence of local or national guidelines on antibacterial prescribing)
- process indicators (e.g. duration of antibacterial therapy or performing of relevant diagnostic tests before antibacterial prescriptions)
- outcome indicators, which focus on consequences of interventions (e.g. total antibacterial use in DDD per 1000 inhabitants per day or resistance rates of community acquired infection-causing pathogens)

Indicators can be described as quality or quantity metrics. Quality metrics can be used to measure the quality of antimicrobial use. [25] For example, clinical indications are used to assess if a given treatment is pursuant to guidelines addressing these indications. [4-6] Quantity metrics are numerical measures reflecting the volume of antibiotic use, consumption (aggregated national- or regional-level data, e.g. sales data) or prescription (patient-level data). [24] For example, defined daily doses (DDD) per 1000 inhabitants per day as used by the World Health Organization (ATC/DDD Index 2024). [23]

The evaluation of antibacterial consumption and prescription using metrics is dependent on the availability and nature of the investigated data. For example, most health insurance claims data sets do not contain clinical indications. Nevertheless, clinical indications are often used to define quality indicators. Missing clinical indications, hence, make it impossible to determine such quality indicators.

To bridge this gap proxy indicators were established. Proxy indicators do share some of the characteristics of both quantity and quality indicators. They are derived from quantity metrics, but can indirectly reflect appropriateness of healthcare if associated with a target value. For example, seasonal variation of antibiotic consumption may act as such a proxy indicator: an example, overprescribing of antibiotics in winter might be the result of inappropriate antibiotic use for viral infections. [4]

The latest systematic compilation of literature dealing with such metrics split into quantity and quality metrics happened in 2014 and was conducted by the Driving Reinvestment in Research and Development and Responsible Antibiotic Use (DRIVE-AB) working group and published in 2018. [5, 6] Additionally, a narrative review, giving an overview of metrics that evaluate antibacterial drug use and prescription in the ambulatory healthcare setting, was published in 2021 by Valerie Leung et al. [7]

However, to the best of our knowledge, no newer systematic literature review was performed for the two metrics measuring quantity and quality in the area of antibiotic use, consumption or prescription in the outpatient setting.

Methods

This scoping review will gather qualitative and quantitative metrics evaluating antibiotic prescription and consumption in the outpatient population in order to support and improve antibiotic stewardship in this healthcare setting.

We will follow the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) extensions for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR) checklist to write-up this protocol (see [Supplementary](#) section for the completed PRISMA-ScR checklist) and we will adhere to the same PRISMA extensions for reporting and writing the final scoping review (PRISMA-ScR). [8]

To conduct the scoping review, the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology will additionally be applied. [9]

The scoping review will consist of the definition of the research question ("*What metrics are described in the scientific literature that evaluate antibiotic prescription and consumption in the outpatient setting?*"), the compilation of the search strategy with subsequent validation and peer-review performed by a medical information specialist, execution of the search strategy in Medline and Embase via Ovid with additional manual searches through websites and citation chasing of relevant publications, and two blinded screening phases (titles and abstracts, full-texts), conducted by two independent reviewers (TH and JD). If discrepancies within the screening occurs, they will be resolved via consensus or guiding of a third party (CPS). Finally, found studies will be extracted into EndNote Version X9.3.3 Build 13966 (Clarivate Analytics LLC, United States of America), the deduplication and following screening will then be performed in Rayyan (Rayyan Systems, Cambridge, Massachusetts, United States of America). [10]

Data will be extracted by one researcher (TH) and the extraction will be verified by another author (JD or CPS).

Eligibility criteria

In this scoping review we will include studies that present quantitative or qualitative metrics for systemic antibiotic use in the outpatient setting written in English and published between January 1st 2021 and March 5th 2025. Table 1 presents the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 1 Inclusion and exclusion criteria for the selection of articles in the scoping review according to the PEO (Population, Exposure, Outcome) framework

PEO	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Population	Outpatient health care structures incl. emergency departments (for detailed definition see Eligibility criteria flowtext)	Inpatient settings, nursing homes, veterinarian studies, environmental studies,

		outpatient parenteral antimicrobial therapy (OPAT)
Exposure	Antibacterials for systemic use	Antibiotic resistance Studies looking exclusively at non-systemic antibiotics (e.g. topical or inhaled antibiotics) Antiviral, antifungal, antiparasitic, antitreponemal, antihelminthics or leprostatic agents, antimalaria or tuberculosis antibiotics
Outcomes	Quantitative, qualitative metric or proxy indicators (see respective definition in the Rationale)	--
Study Design	Quantitative studies and qualitative studies as well as mixed-method studies	Case reports, case series, pre-clinical studies, basic science research (e.g. in-vitro studies)
Other	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Language	English	Other languages
Publication date	January 1 st 2021 to March 5 th 2025	--
Publication type	Original articles and systematic reviews, reports on surveillance data from national and supranational entities (see list of websites)	Study protocols, replies / comments / responses to studies, summaries of studies (incl. executive summaries of studies), corrections of studies (errata), editorials, opinion papers, conference abstracts, conference papers and conference reviews, letters, notes

The outpatient setting is defined as practices or facilities such as outpatient clinics, general practices, ambulatory care facilities, family medicine practices, pharmacies, dentists and outpatient departments of hospitals. Additionally, we will include emergency departments, because in some regions and countries patients rely on outpatient clinics and emergency departments for ambulatory care. [11, 12] Studies without available abstracts will be included in the full-text screening directly. We will exclude antiviral, antifungal, antiparasitic, antitreponemal, antimalaria, anthelmintic and leprostatic agents as well as tuberculosis agents. In order for articles to be included they will need to mention some metric that evaluates antibiotic consumption or prescription data stemming from outpatient healthcare structures, divided into three non-exhaustive categories (quality metrics, quantity metrics and proxy indicators) inspired by the publication of Nathalie Thilly et al., 2017 (for the definition of these categories please see [Rationale](#)). [4]

Studies that are solely mentioning metrics of antibiotic resistance will be excluded. Furthermore, articles exclusively referencing nursing homes, an inpatient setting, outpatient parenteral antimicrobial therapy (OPAT), environmental studies or veterinary studies will be excluded. We will also exclude publications where no methodology is explained about how the monitoring was conducted or how the indicator or metrics were calculated (this can also simply be a further reference, where methodology is explained).

We will not impose any limitations concerning regions, countries, ethnicities, genders and age groups. The exclusion criteria regarding publication types will be study protocols, replies / comments /

responses to studies, summaries of studies (incl. executive summaries of studies), corrections of studies (errata), editorials, opinion papers, conference abstracts, conference papers and conference reviews, letters and notes. If the study design is of quantitative, qualitative or mixed-methods character we will include it, otherwise it will be excluded. And lastly, articles where both reviewers or other authors, and the respective institutions do not have access to a full text will be excluded. The included articles (after the full-text screening) will be manually searched for added corrections and whether these corrections are relevant for the metrics of interest. If that is the case, the corrections will be considered and only afterwards will the metrics be extracted.

Information sources

We will retrieve articles from Medline and Embase via Ovid, and articles or guidelines from several pre-defined websites (see [list of websites in the Supplementary](#)). This website search will be conducted by one reviewer only (TH). Publications in Medline and Embase from 2021 to March 5th 2025 will be examined. This limitation concerning the publication date could potentially lead to bias, however there was a very similar literature review conducted by Versporten et al. and Le Maréchal et al. up until the end of 2014. [5, 6] Additionally, we will perform small manual searches and include relevant resulting articles as well (TH). Relevance of such publications will be determined by discussion with the research team (CPS and JD). With the extracted full texts, we will perform backward citation chasing, preferably with the tool "citationchaser". [14]

Search strategy

The search strategy will be established revolving around three key concepts (according to the PEO framework – see Table 2; population, exposure and outcome): "outpatients", "antibacterial agents" and "metric". All three concepts include indexing key terms as well as free text terms connected with the Boolean operator "OR". The complementary search will be performed using the Boolean operator "AND" to unite all three concepts. The search strategy will be validated and peer-reviewed by a medical information specialist from the Medical Library of the University of Bern and afterwards reviewed by another medical information specialist from the Medical Library of the University of Basel.

Table 2 Search strategy: Key concepts according to the PEO framework

PEO framework	Key concept	Connecting Boolean operator
Population	Outpatient population	AND
Exposure	Antibacterial agents	AND
Outcome	Metric	

The complete search queries can be found in the Supplementary [Search query](#).

The literature that thematizes the target topic contains a complex problem: the third concept – being the "metric or indicator" one – proves to be rather hard to grasp. Hence, the generation of a search query including this concept leads to a quite heterogenous and broad landscape of results while potentially still missing out on some relevant publications. This issue also resulted in several limitations (e.g. language and publication year) that will be needed to be imposed in order to perform this review in a timely manner. Furthermore, we will not explode the key terms revolving around "antibacterial agents", that is because if we would do so, it would be required to also include hundreds of antibacterial active ingredient names within the free text search. That would not be expedient for our research questions, nevertheless not doing so could again lead to missing a few relevant hits. However, this makes our review question suitable for a scoping review. As the goal of a scoping review is to map and summarize key concepts of broad research areas rather than answer precise research questions. [9] Additionally, we will conduct a search with a list of websites (that we previously determined, see [List of Websites](#)) and backward citation search to fill these resulting gaps.

Accordingly, before the search strategy will be finalized osf.ch, zenodo.org and comet-initiative.org will be manually searched using the two concepts "outpatient" and "antibiotic" in order to find out if an identical project was planned or carried out recently. If applicable filters such as "publication date", "subject" (e.g. antibiotics, antibiotic resistance), "intervention", "disease type" (e.g. infectious diseases or public health) will be employed. On osf.org overlapping projects will be checked for the years 2023 and 2024 solely, filters will be applied when using zenodo.org or comet-initiative.org. However, we have to disclaim that the results for these three websites will not be exhaustive, simply because there is no way to check these websites systematically.

There are some scoping reviews registered that have similarities to ours. One registered and already completed study on comet-initiative.org is the one by Rebekah W. Moehring et al., later published in the Journal "Clinical Infectious Diseases" and bearing the title "Expert Consensus on Metrics to Assess the Impact of Patient-Level Antimicrobial Stewardship Interventions in Acute-Care Settings". However, they solely addressed acute care hospitals, and their search was finalized by the end of 2015. [15] Another protocol was registered on osf.org by Nathaly Garzón-Orjuela et al. titled "Setting targets for antibiotic use in general practice in European countries: a scoping review protocol" and their article was recently published. [16] Yet they do focus more specifically on finding existing targets for antibiotic use and setting them rather than metrics or studies that evaluate antibiotic use and prescription. Furthermore, they are interested in targets for general practices specifically and not having a look at the whole outpatient healthcare setting. Then there are the three already mentioned publications: Two by the DRIVE-AB group [5, 6] performed in 2014 and published in 2018. And one by Valerie Leung et al. [7] published in 2021, however the goal of this scoping review is to compile an update on metrics that evaluate antibacterial use and prescription in the outpatient setting.

Data management

The articles found in Medline and Embase will be extracted into EndNote Version X9.3.3 Build 13966 (Clarivate Analytics LLC, United States of America), the deduplication and subsequent two blinded screening phases will be conducted with Rayyan (Rayyan Systems, Cambridge, Massachusetts, United States of America). [10]

Selection of sources of evidence

Having conducted the deduplication, a first screening phase will be started in Rayyan: two independent reviewers (TH and JD) will check the eligibility of the studies by screening titles and abstracts of the articles. If the studies do meet the inclusion criteria they will be included into the full-text screening. In the case of a disagreement between the two reviewers, this will be solved via consensus discussion or guidance of a third party (CPS). However, if there still is uncertainty the article will be included in the next screening phase. Afterwards, full texts will be extracted for articles that were included and two independent reviewers (TH and JD) will again compare the eligibility criteria with the full texts and decide if the studies get in- or excluded. Again, if conflict appears, it will be solved with a discussion in order to reach an agreement.

Data charting process

Extracted data will be recorded in a predefined extraction sheet created using MS Excel at least being of Version 1808 Build 10412.20006 Klick-und-Los (Microsoft Corporation, Washington, United States). One researcher (TH) will extract the data and another will verify the extraction (JD or CPS). If conflicts appear they will be resolved by consensus discussions.

Data items

General information about eligible articles will be collected, such as author names, year of publication, origin of study (or study population), setting (outpatient only, outpatient in hospitals, etc.), study design, outcomes and / or metrics relevant for the study aim will be collected and then further categorized (see Figure 3).

The cut-off value for the final inclusion of the measure into the RAND-modified Delphi study is XXXX .	Ann Versporten et al., 2018	Marion Le Maréchal et al., 2018
Quantity Def.; Quantity metrics, are mentioned as a numerical measure reflecting the volume of antibiotic use or consumption. For example, defined daily doses (DDD) per 1000 inhabitants per day as used by the World Health Organization (ATC/DDD Index 2024)		
DDDs per defined population	x	
Treatments/courses per defined population	x	
treatments/courses per defined number of physician contacts	x	
prescriptions per defined population	x	
prescriptions per defined number of physician contacts	x	
seasonal variation of total antibiotic use	x	

Figure 1 Example extraction sheet to measure how many times a specific metric was mentioned.

Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence

In accordance with the JBI-methodologies no critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence will be performed [9].

Synthesis of results

The results will be presented narratively. Data extraction will be performed using a predefined extraction table created according to Danielle Pollock et al. and the JBI-methodology (see Figures 2 and 3). [9, 17]

A descriptive analysis will be performed including all studies retained after the second screening. In an overview information on which region the studies investigated (e.g. low-income countries, lower-middle-income countries, upper-middle-income countries, high-income countries) categorized according to the World Bank Group will be provided. [19] Age groups (e.g. children vs. adults) and gender distributions of the review population will be calculated with descriptive statistics if applicable. We will also count how many times a particular metric is mentioned in the articles searched (see Figure 2).

Several studies mention different kind of outpatient settings; hence we will quantify which health care settings are mentioned specifically and present respective proportions:

- GPs (e.g. GP practices, family medicine, group practices, family physicians incl. the ones in primary healthcare centers, primary care facilities, primary healthcare centers, group practices)
- Pharmacies
- Specialist outpatient practices (e.g. gynecologists, pediatricians, cardiologists, dentists)
- Outpatient hospital departments, outpatient clinics, emergency departments

Further, we will group the metrics (see Figure 3, section "outcomes") into proxy indicators, quantity metrics and quality indicators. The latter being further divided into structural, process and outcome quality indicators. We will note which articles included do address local, national or international metrics. Generally, we will also categorize the identified metrics into consumption- and prescription-associated metrics. Additionally, we will tabulate how many articles are giving targets for their respective indicators / metrics and if they mention targets list them accordingly. This listing of data synthesis is not exhaustive and might be adjusted later on. Please see Figure 3 for an example of how the extraction sheet could look like.

Nr	Author, Year	Country	Localisation	Socioecological si	Aim	Study type	Population	Sample size	Age (yrs)	Gender	Other deme	Setting	Exposure	Outcomes (measure)	Target
Description	Name of authors (if two: Martina Müller & Alex Smith, if more than two: Martina Müller et al.), Publication Year, DOI	country of origin of study, if the study took place in multiple countries list them. If a review was done name the inclusion criteria for the region, e.g. Europe, EU, Scandinavian countries, worldwide, etc.	If metrics were collected, measured or developed for a local, national or international setting	If country of origin (definition see column "Country") is labelled as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high-income • upper-middle-income • lower-middle-income • or low-income according to the World Bank Group (see link above) 	Describe the aim or objective of the study.	Describe the study type: e.g. quantitative, qualitative, mixed-methods and design: e.g. scoping review, literature review (scoping review)	Describe the study population and the respective definition used within the study if applicable.	Fill in sample size of the study if applicable.	Fill in age of the study population if applicable.	Fill in gender of the study population (female, male, both, diverse or not distinguished)	Describe other important demographics.	Describe investigated setting: GPs&primary care facilities, specialist outpatient clinics or outpatient hospital departments	Exposure will be anyway to antibiotics, describe if measure is associated to consumption, prescription or both.	Describe if quantity, quality or proxy measures (or a mixture of them) are named within the study. (Further extraction of the measures see separate outcome extraction file).	Describe targets mentioned for measures within the study if applicable.
1	Ann Versporten et al., 2018	worldwide	international	high-income	To identify consensually validated quantity metrics for antibiotic use in the outpatient setting.	Qualitative (Systematic review + RAND-modified Delphi procedure)	Outpatient: A patient who is not hospitalized and visits a physician in the ambulatory care setting or ambulatory patients who visit physicians	-	-	not declared	-	all (GPs&primary care facilities, specialist outpatient practices, outpatient hospital departments)	both (consumption&prescription)	quantity	-

Figure 2 Example extraction sheet adapted according to Pollock et al. and the JBI-methodology.

The goal of this scoping review is to unveil various metrics for the assessment of antibiotic use, it shall compile an updated overview of such metrics and create a better understanding for the landscape of antibiotic consumption and prescription metrics. Hence a quality assessment of the individual metrics extracted would go beyond the scope of this review and will not be implemented. All the sections concerning quality assessment drawn from the PRISMA guidelines are thus not included in this protocol. [20]

The PRISMA-ScR checklist can be found in the [Supplementary \(Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews\)](#).

Lastly, this scoping review will be published in a peer-reviewed journal and might also be presented at conferences. Additionally, the ultimate goal is to generate a core set of metrics that evaluate antibiotic prescription and consumption in the outpatient healthcare setting in Switzerland. Therefore, a RAND-modified Delphi study will be performed afterwards in order to prioritize metrics for inclusion.

Limitations

Only two databases will be searched in order to perform this scoping review, additionally the search was confined to languages (inclusion of English articles solely) and to a specific publication period (exclusion of publication dates before 2021). Several other containments were made on the search strategy such as not exploding key terms for anti-bacterial agents or using the unsharp concept revolving around "metric" (for details see [Search strategy](#) under the Methods section). To minimize the potentially resulting gap, we will perform website searches and backward citation searching.

Confidence in cumulative evidence

This scoping review will not inspect validation of the found metrics, hence no cumulative evidence will be generated but a list of metrics that evaluate outpatient antibiotic consumption.

Quality Assessment

According to the JBI-methodology [9], a quality assessment is not mandatory for a scoping review. Therefore, no quality assessment of included studies or potential bias in the context of this scoping review will be carried out.

Study status

The search strategy in the electronic databases was already performed on March 5th 2025 and the reviewers have started the first screening process (titles and abstracts) but not finished yet. Furthermore, the manual search for similar or identical projects was completed. The manual searches for additional eligible and relevant studies are still undergoing.

Support

Funding

No external funding was received.

Declarations

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Competing interests

There are no competing interests to declare.

Contributions

TH, CPS and CMM were involved in the development of the research question and the search strategy. All authors contributed to the advancement of the search strategy and the review methodology. TH and JD will perform the two screening processes. TH drafted the protocol manuscript. All authors provided feedback on the draft and approved the final version. CPS and AK are the guarantors of this protocol.

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Supplementary

Search query

Figure 3 Search query for Medline via Ovid

#	Query
1	anti-infective agents/ or anti-bacterial agents/
2	(Anti-Bacterial? or Antibacterial? or Antibiotic? or Bacteriocid* or Bactericid* or Anti-Microbial* or Antimicrobial*).ti,ab,kw.
3	1 or 2
4	exp ambulatory care/ or exp ambulatory care facilities/ or exp community health centers/ or exp community health services/ or exp community pharmacy services/ or exp outpatients/ or exp general practitioners/ or exp general practice/ or exp family practice/ or exp physicians, family/ or exp physicians, primary care/ or exp office visits/ or exp primary health care/ or exp group practice/
5	((ambulatory or ambulant or primary) adj3 (care* or patient? or service? or health*)) or "clinic visit*" or outpatient* or out-patient* or "urgent care*" or "general pract*" or "family pract*" or "family physician?" or "family medicine?" or "first line care?" or "primary care physician?" or "primary healthcare*" or "primary health care?" or "day patient*" or "community health*" or "community pharmacy service?" or "community care?" or "pharmacy (shop)" or "group practice*" or "health center?").ti,ab,kw.
6	4 or 5
7	exp quality assurance, health care/ or exp benchmarking/ or exp potentially inappropriate medication list/ or exp "public reporting of healthcare data"/ or exp "utilization review"/ or exp "drug utilization review"/ or exp "drug utilization"/ or exp quality indicators, health care/ or exp epidemiological monitoring/ or exp practice patterns, physicians/ or exp inappropriate prescribing/ or exp drug prescriptions/ or exp medication errors/ or exp prescription drug misuse/ or exp clinical audit/ or exp clinical pathways/ or exp guideline adherence/ or exp drug evaluation study/
8	("public reporting of health care data" or "public reporting (health care)" or benchmark* or metric* or standard* or parameter* or criteri* or "health?care quality" or "quality of healthcare" or "quality healthcare indicator*" or "quality assessment?" or "quality assurance?" or "best practice analy*" or "physician practice pattern*" or indicator* or "best practice analy*" or "utili?ation review?" or "drug utili?ation" or "medication error?" or monitoring? or surveillance? or "prescription drug misuse*" or "prescribing error?" or "clinical audit*" or "clinical practice?" or "clinical pathway*" or "guideline adherence*" or "drug evaluation stud*" or "protocol compliance?" or "potentially inappropriate medication" or "medication error?" or "drug screening?").ti,ab,kw.
9	((appropriat* or inappropriat*) adj3 (prescri* or use* or usage* or consumption* or medication*)).ti,ab,kw.
10	7 or 8 or 9
11	3 and 6 and 10
12	limit 11 to (english language and yr="2021 -Current")

Figure 4 Search query for Embase via Ovid

#	Query
1	antiinfective agent/ or antibiotic agent/
2	(Anti-Bacterial? or Antibacterial? or Antibiotic? or Bacteriocid* or Bactericid* or Anti-Microbial* or Antimicrobial*).tw,ab,kw.
3	1 or 2
4	exp ambulatory care/ or exp outpatient department/ or exp health center/ or exp community care/ or exp "pharmacy (shop)"/ or exp outpatient/ or exp general practitioner/ or exp general practice/ or exp primary health care/ or exp group practice/
5	((((ambulatory or ambulant or primary) adj3 (care* or patient? or service? or health*)) or "clinic visit*" or outpatient* or out-patient* or "urgent care*" or "general pract*" or "family pract*" or "family physician?" or "family medicine?" or "first line care?" or "primary care physician?" or "primary healthcare*" or "primary health care?" or "day patient*" or "community health*" or "community pharmacy service?" or "community care?" or "pharmacy (shop)" or "group practice*" or "health center?").tw,ab,kw.
6	4 or 5
7	exp health care quality/ or exp benchmarking/ or exp potentially inappropriate medication/ or exp "public reporting (health care)"/ or exp utilization review/ or exp drug utilization review/ or exp drug utilization/ or exp epidemiological monitoring/ or exp clinical practice/ or exp prescribing error/ or exp prescription/ or exp medication error/ or exp prescription drug misuse/ or exp clinical audit/ or exp clinical pathway/ or exp protocol compliance/ or exp drug screening/
8	("public reporting of health care data" or "public reporting (health care)" or benchmark* or metric* or standard* or parameter* or criteri* or "health?care quality" or "quality of healthcare" or "quality healthcare indicator*" or "quality assessment?" or "quality assurance?" or "best practice analy*" or "physician practice pattern*" or indicator* or "best practice analy*" or "utili?ation review?" or "drug utili?ation" or "medication error?" or monitoring? or surveillance? or "prescription drug misuse*" or "prescribing error?" or "clinical audit*" or "clinical practice?" or "clinical pathway*" or "guideline adherence*" or "drug evaluation stud*" or "protocol compliance?" or "potentially inappropriate medication" or "medication error?" or "drug screening?").tw,ab,kw.
9	((appropriat* or inappropriat*) adj3 (prescri* or use* or usage* or consumption* or medication*)).tw,ab,kw.
10	7 or 8 or 9
11	3 and 6 and 10
12	limit 11 to (english language and yr="2021 -Current")
13	(conference abstract or conference paper or conference review or editorial or erratum or letter or note).pt.

14	12 not 13
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List of abbreviations

AMR	Antimicrobial resistance
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutical Chemical (acc. To WHO)
DDD	Defined daily doses [13]
DRIVE-AB	Driving Reinvestment in Research and Development and Responsible Antibiotic Use
JBI	Joanna Briggs Institute [9]
OPAT	Outpatient Parenteral Antimicrobial Therapy
PEO	Population, Exposure, Outcome
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses
PRISMA-ScR	PRISMA extension for Scoping Reviews
RAND	Originated as a contraction of <u>R</u> esearch and <u>D</u> evelopment [21]
WHO	World health organization

Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist

According to the PRISMA extension for scoping reviews and adapted for the reporting of a protocol for a scoping review [8].

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	1
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	1
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	2
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	2
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	This checklist refers to the protocol that will be registered.
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	3
Information sources*	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	5
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	5
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	6
Data charting process‡	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	6
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	6
Critical appraisal of individual	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this	6

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
sources of evidence§		information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	7
RESULTS			
Selection of sources of evidence	14	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	na
Characteristics of sources of evidence	15	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	na
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	na
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	na
Synthesis of results	18	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	na
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	na
Limitations	20	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	na
Conclusions	21	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	na
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	9

JBI = Joanna Briggs Institute; PRISMA-ScR = Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews.

* Where *sources of evidence* (see second footnote) are compiled from, such as bibliographic databases, social media platforms, and Web sites.

† A more inclusive/heterogeneous term used to account for the different types of evidence or data sources (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy documents) that may be eligible in a scoping review as opposed to only studies. This is not to be confused with *information sources* (see first footnote).

‡ The frameworks by Arksey and O'Malley (6) and Levac and colleagues (7) and the JBI guidance (4, 5) refer to the process of data extraction in a scoping review as data charting.

§ The process of systematically examining research evidence to assess its validity, results, and relevance before using it to inform a decision. This term is used for items 12 and 19 instead of "risk of bias" (which is more applicable to systematic reviews of interventions) to include and acknowledge the various sources of evidence that may be used in a scoping review (e.g., quantitative and/or qualitative research, expert opinion, and policy document).

From: Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;169:467–473. doi: [10.7326/M18-0850](https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-0850).

List of Websites

Name of organisation/institution	Link
Agency for Healthcare Research & Quality	https://www.ahrq.gov/
Alliance for the Prudent Use of Antibiotics (APUA)	www.apua.org/
AMR local indicators - produced by the UKHSA	https://fingertips.phe.org.uk/profile/amr-local-indicators
Antibiotic Centre for Primary Care	https://www.med.uio.no/helsam/english/research/groups/general-practice-medicine/asp/
Australian Government Department of Health and Aged Care	https://www.health.gov.au/
Canadian Centre for Rural and Agricultural Health	https://cchsa-ccssma.usask.ca/
Collection: Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) (UK government)	https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/antimicrobial-resistance-amr-information-and-resources
Dutch Working Party on Antibiotic Policy (SWAB)	http://www.swab.nl/
English surveillance programme for antimicrobial utilisation and resistance (ESPAUR) report	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/english-surveillance-programme-antimicrobial-utilisation-and-resistance-espaur-report
European Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (ECDC)	www.ecdc.europa.eu/
European General Practice Research Network (EGPRN)	https://www.egprn.org/
European Medicines Agency (EMA)	www.ema.europa.eu/
European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases (ESCMID)	https://www.escmid.org/
General practice Research on Infections Network (GRIN)	https://www.grinweb.org/
German Society of General Practice/Family Medicine (DEGAM)	https://www.degam.de/
Infectious Disease Society of America (IDSA)	https://www.idsociety.org/
Institute for Healthcare Improvement	https://www.ihl.org/
International Society of Infectious Diseases	https://isid.org/
Irish College of General Practitioners (ICGP)	https://www.icgp.ie/
Management Sciences for Health	https://msh.org/

National Institute for Health and Care Excellence	https://www.nice.org.uk/
National Health Service (NHS)	https://www.england.nhs.uk/
Public Health Agency of Canada	https://www.canada.ca/en/public-health.html
RAND Corporation	https://www.rand.org/
ReAct group	https://www.reactgroup.org/
Royal College of General Practitioners (RCGP)	https://www.rcgp.org.uk/
Swedish Strategic Programme Against Antibiotic Resistance (Strama)	https://strama.se/?lang=en
The British Society for Antimicrobial Chemotherapy (BSAC)	http://www.bsac.org.uk/
The Center for Disease Dynamics, Economics & Policy (CDDEP)	https://onehealthtrust.org/
The Global Antibiotic Resistance Partnership (GARP)	https://onehealthtrust.org/projects/global-antibiotic-resistance-partnership/
Train-the-Trainer Event: Defining and Implementing Responsible Antibiotic Use (DRIVE-AB)	http://drive-ab.eu/events/train-the-trainer-event-defining-and-implementing-responsible-antibiotic-use/
Transatlantic Task Force on Antimicrobial Resistance (TATFAR)	https://www.cdc.gov/tatfar/php/about/index.html
U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)	https://www.cdc.gov/
U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA)	https://www.fda.gov/
WONCA Europe: World family doctors. Caring for people.	https://www.woncaeurope.org/
World Health Organization (WHO)	www.who.int/
Scottish Antimicrobial Prescribing Group	https://www.sapg.scot/
Ministère de la santé et de la prévention (France): direction de la recherche, des études, de l'évaluation et des statistiques (DREES)	https://drees.shinyapps.io/prescription-antibios-MG/
OECD – Antibiotic Resistance	https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/antimicrobial-resistance.html#:~:text=Note%3A%20The%20One%20Health%20package,Approach%20to%20Fight%20Antimicrobial%20Resistance%22.

WHO – GLASS	https://www.who.int/initiatives/glass
ESGAP	https://www.escmid.org/esgap/
Public Health Ontario	https://www.publichealthontario.ca/en/Health-Topics/Antimicrobial-Stewardship/Primary-Care

These websites were compiled by TH, CPS, JD and YM and further detailed according to [5, 6, 16]

References

1. Murray, C.J.L., et al., *Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis*. The Lancet, 2022. **399**(10325): p. 629-655.
2. Bell, B.G., et al., *A systematic review and meta-analysis of the effects of antibiotic consumption on antibiotic resistance*. BMC Infect Dis, 2014. **14**: p. 13.
3. Dyar, O.J., et al., *What is antimicrobial stewardship?* Clin Microbiol Infect, 2017. **23**(11): p. 793-798.
4. Thilly, N., et al., *Proxy indicators to estimate appropriateness of antibiotic prescriptions by general practitioners: a proof-of-concept cross-sectional study based on reimbursement data, north-eastern France 2017*. Euro Surveillance: Bulletin Européen sur les Maladies Transmissibles = European Communicable Disease Bulletin, 2020. **25**(27): p. 07.
5. Le Marechal, M., et al., *Quality indicators assessing antibiotic use in the outpatient setting: a systematic review followed by an international multidisciplinary consensus procedure*. Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy, 2018. **73**(suppl_6): p. vi40-vi49.
6. Versporten, A., et al., *Metrics to assess the quantity of antibiotic use in the outpatient setting: a systematic review followed by an international multidisciplinary consensus procedure*. Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy, 2018. **73**(suppl_6): p. vi59-vi66.
7. Leung, V., et al., *Metrics for evaluating antibiotic use and prescribing in outpatient settings*. JAC-antimicrobial Resistance, 2021. **3**(3): p. dlab098.
8. Tricco, A.C., et al., *PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation*. Ann Intern Med, 2018. **169**(7): p. 467-473.
9. von Elm, E., G. Schreiber, and C.C. Haupt, [Not Available]. Z Evid Fortbild Qual Gesundheitswes, 2019. **143**: p. 1-7.
10. Ouzzani, M., et al., *Rayyan-a web and mobile app for systematic reviews*. Syst Rev, 2016. **5**(1): p. 210.
11. Vogel, J.A., et al., *Reasons Patients Choose the Emergency Department over Primary Care: a Qualitative Metasynthesis*. J Gen Intern Med, 2019. **34**(11): p. 2610-2619.
12. Bank, W.H.O.a.I.B.f.R.a.D.T.W., *Global monitoring report on financial protection in health 2021*. 2021.
13. Methodology, W.C.C.f.D.S., *Guidelines for ATC classification and DDD assignment 2024*. 2023.
14. Haddaway, N.R., M.J. Grainger, and C.T. Gray, *Citationchaser: A tool for transparent and efficient forward and backward citation chasing in systematic searching*. Res Synth Methods, 2022. **13**(4): p. 533-545.
15. Moehring, R.W., et al., *Expert Consensus on Metrics to Assess the Impact of Patient-Level Antimicrobial Stewardship Interventions in Acute-Care Settings*. Clin Infect Dis, 2017. **64**(3): p. 377-383.
16. Garzon-Orjuela, N., et al., *Setting targets for antibiotic use in general practice in Europe: A scoping review*. European Journal of General Practice. **30**(1): p. 2430507.
17. Pollock, D., et al., *Recommendations for the extraction, analysis, and presentation of results in scoping reviews*. JBI Evid Synth, 2023. **21**(3): p. 520-532.
18. Adriaenssens, N., et al., *Consumption of quinolones in the community, European Union/European Economic Area, 1997-2017*. Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy, 2021. **76**(12 Suppl 2): p. ii37-ii44.
19. Group, W.B.; Available from: <https://datatopics.worldbank.org/world-development-indicators/the-world-by-income-and-region.html#:~:text=The%20World%20Bank%20classifies%20economies,%20middle%2C%20and%20high%20income>.
20. Shamseer, L., et al., *Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation*. Bmj, 2015. **350**: p. g7647.
21. Fitch, K., et al., *The RAND/UCLA Appropriateness Method User's Manual*. 2001, Santa Monica, CA: RAND Corporation.

22. WHO, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/antimicrobial-resistance>, accessed 21.10.2024
23. WHO, ATC/DDD Index 2024, https://atcddd.fhi.no/atc_ddd_index/, accessed 23.10.2024
24. Browne AJ, Chipeta MG, Haines-Woodhouse G, Kumaran EPA, Hamadani BHK, Zaraa S, Henry NJ, Deshpande A, Reiner RC Jr, Day NPJ, Lopez AD, Dunachie S, Moore CE, Stergachis A, Hay SI, Dolecek C. *Global antibiotic consumption and usage in humans, 2000-18: a spatial modelling study*. Lancet Planet Health. 2021 Dec;5(12):e893-e904. doi: 10.1016/S2542-5196(21)00280-1. Epub 2021 Nov 12. PMID: 34774223; PMCID: PMC8654683.
25. Stemkens R, Schouten JA, van Kessel SAM, Akkermans RP, Telgt DSC, Fleuren HWWA, Claassen MAA, Hulscher MEJL, Ten Oever J. *How to use quality indicators for antimicrobial stewardship in your hospital: a practical example on outpatient parenteral antimicrobial therapy*. Clin Microbiol Infect. 2023 Feb;29(2):182-187. doi: 10.1016/j.cmi.2022.07.007. Epub 2022 Jul 15. PMID: 35843564.